

HISTORY OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In our scientific work, information is given in chronological order about the history of gastronomic tourism, which is an important type of tourism, in Uzbekistan, as well as details of the reforms implemented in this field during the years of independence and future plans, the importance of the role of this type in the tourism industry, information about gastronomic associations. information provided. , institutions and organizations. Today's achievements in the field of gastronomic tourism are partially highlighted, the internal possibilities of this type are widely shown, and a number of scientific and practical suggestions for the development of gastronomic tourism are given.

Key words: cuisine, national cuisine, gastronomic tourism, food and beverage, events, history, cooking.

"Food tourism is developing in the world for two main reasons: first, the desire of people to know where their food came from, and second, the desire to discover new foods and cooking" [1, p. 3].

The term gastronomic tourism was first used in 1998 by scientists at Bowling Green University (USA), and although the term has not gone back a long way, we can find a lot of information about food and beverages in our country in historical works. This creates a unique history of gastronomic tourism. There are many local and foreign sources describing the travels in the territory of Uzbekistan. Our ancient ancestors migrated to different lands as nomads during their social life. They enjoy the natural pleasures of grazing, living in pastures, drinking clear water, consuming milk, yogurt, meat and fruits, as well as seeking nutrients and herbs that are not in the same area due to the need for medical treatment. had to travel. According to historical legends, even Alexander the Great came to Central Asia in search of "magical water" that would prolong life and rejuvenate man[2,p.7]. At this point, the Great Silk Road, as the main trade route connecting east and west, carried food along with various goods, which means that it played an important role in gastronomic tourism of that period. For example, rice was brought to Central Asia from China, and from there grapes, nuts, pomegranates and other agricultural products were exported to China.

Since the main occupations of the first medieval states in our country: Sogdiana, Fergana, Takharistan, Eftallar, Kidariy were agriculture and animal husbandry, their food consisted of various fruits and vegetables, dairy products and meat products [3]. This situation did not change much during the later Turkish empire and Arab rule, but after the Mongol invasion in our country there were great changes in the food of the settled population. This was due to the existence of differences in the specific eating customs and rules of the Mongols. As the Mongols were a nomadic people, their main food consisted of meat and dairy products. Kurut would replace food for them during a quick move. But where conditions were right, they could boil meat in their small cauldrons and drink the blood of horses in the absence of dried or other food, so that they could be fed in this way for ten days.”[4]

Genghis Khan insisted on maintaining the honor of the guest in the desert, and had enshrined in law that if a man was eating, he must invite the man next to him to be his partner. Everyone would partner with the person eating without being invited. During the Mongols, he held the position of "Yurtchi". As they marched through desert and arid lands, they had to determine how much food and water the army needed, and generally know where there was drinking water and fodder along the way[5, p.31]. Accordingly, they stockpiled spare food. The Mongols also had a nomadic-style way of eating.

The nutrition of the Mongols and the supply of food to the army were greatly improved later in the Timurid period. “Along with Amir Temur's army, butchers, bakuls, traders of roasted and cooked meat, sellers of barley and fruit, and bakers also moved. Gathering food for the army was important. This task was entrusted to commanders such as Allahdod and White Temur Bahadir”[6, p.93]. They provided the army with the necessary food before the battle.

From the above information, it can be concluded that Amir Temur used food as a form of punishment for the army, as well as used it as an incentive. "After the victory in the battle against the ceasefire, Amir Temur, in accordance with his tradition, rewarded those who showed courage, entertained the warriors with various delicacies and rewarded them with koumiss in expensive vessels"[7, p. 151].

Zakhriddin Muhammad Babur also describes in his work "Boburnoma" the various delicacies, fruits and melons of our country, noting that their taste is not found in other countries. During the Timurid period, dining and hospitality continued in Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand empires. Information about the cuisine of this period can be found in the works and memoirs of many foreign tourists.

Alikhan Gafur, an Iranian ambassador who met the khan of Khiva in 1842, described in his diary: Wherever they love horses or yabu, their stubbornness and lust belong to him. No one has the right to eat it, it is collected only for the khan. The khan cleans, grinds and cooks them with his own hands. This is his best and most delicious dish.”[9]

During the war years, the state was supplied with surplus foodstuffs such as vegetables, rhizomes, fruits, meat, and grain. In particular, 82 million pounds of grain, 1.1 million tons of rice, 57.5 thousand tons of fruits and grapes, 159.3 thousand tons of meat and other products. -400 grams of bread were given [11, p. 93].

Even in the post-war years, the pursuit of increasing cotton yields by the policies of the dictatorial Soviet government limited the republic's ability to solve its food problems”[12].

Since August 31, 1991, when Uzbekistan gained its independence, positive changes have begun in all spheres in our country, the living standards of the population have improved, freedom of food and freedom of grain have been achieved. Bilateral and multilateral cooperation with foreign countries is being established in every field.

In fact, in the villages located in the provinces, there are only national dishes that are unique to this place, and its taste and composition are not repeated in the villages of other provinces. It is in this sense that such dishes are delicious for both foreign tourists and locals. Our country has all the dishes and beverages that correspond to the four seasons, have a unique ancient history, as well as necessary for human life, for example, radish snack with sour cream in the spring, soup soup, sumalak, halim, blue chuchvara, blue somsa, kovatok rice (vine), roasted cauliflower, mint. In summer, tomato kebab, cabbage stuffing, dumbil soup, pepper stuffing, lagmon, yoghurt soup, sour cream snack, chalop, chicken soup, steamed kebab, meat stew, vegetable stew, ayran, yak tea, fruit compotes and so on are welcome. In autumn, fried fish, laqqa kebab, barra meat, head soup, quail kebab, behili pilaf, potato manti, honey quince, cut lagmon, pumpkin somsa, etc. are on the table. On frosty days, kazi-karta, pustdumba, mutton pilaf, kart dumba pilaf, qazili pilaf, barra kebab, radish salad, fried soup, moshkichiri, winter fruits, their jams, compotes, peels, vinegar and pickles are consumed [13,p.257]. Uzbekistan is one of the top five countries in the CIS and CIS countries in the field of gastronomic tourism. We know that it has always been interesting for tourists to get acquainted with the process of preparation of national dishes in the homeland of those dishes.

In 2016 Uzbek palov (pilaf) culture and tradition has been inscribed on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity of UNESCO. It is proposed to additionally add to this list such pearls of the national intangible cultural heritage of the national dishes sumalak and halim. [14,p.43].

Therefore, the role of public organizations, in particular, the Association of Chefs of Uzbekistan, established in 2008, plays a special role in promoting the brand "Uzbek cuisine" in the world. In order to promote Uzbek national cuisine to the world, to increase the flow of tourists to our country, the Chefs Association of Uzbekistan became a member of the World Association of Chefs in 2010 and the World Association of Chefs in 2017. As a result, many foreign festivals, summits and competitions share experience and achieve high results.

CONCLUSION. I think that the suggestions and recommendations we are going to make will also serve to improve the gastronomic tourism activity, as we have mentioned above examples that our country has long been preparing medicinal and nutritious food, and this process naturally attracts the attention of tourists. In order to further develop this area:

To increase the number of fast food outlets, taking into account the fact that, unlike organized tourists, self-organized tourists prefer to eat on the road, use the services of nearby cafes and bars in attractions;

In this regard, training of specialists, certification, organization of special zones, high level of safety of gastronomic tourism, service staff of restaurants included in the kitchen tour project must know foreign languages and the necessary information about the dishes, drinks and products they prepare. Waiters have to play the additional role of kitchen guides almost completely. Tourists should also be familiar with gastronomic monuments and places where they can buy products that are popular in the area;

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